

1 **Carbon fiber/epoxy composite laminates as through-thickness thermoelectric generators**

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8
9 **Abstract**

10 This research study demonstrates a carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) composite laminate
11 with an embedded thermoelectric (TE) enabled glass fiber (GF) ply. The TE-enabled GF
12 functional ply was purposely laminated to create a structural through-thickness thermoelectric
13 generator (TEG). Simultaneously, the highly conductive carbon fiber (CF) reinforcing phase
14 served as electrodes for the device. Tellurium nanowires (NWs) were incorporated in various
15 mass ratios in a PEDOT:PSS matrix to produce different TE pastes. The TE pastes were
16 deposited on the GF fabrics via a facile blade coating technique. The highest power factor (57.2
17 $\mu\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}^2$, in-plane Seebeck coefficient +189 $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$) was exhibited by the coating formed by
18 the paste with a specific mass ratio of 1:1 (Te NWs to PEDOT:PSS). The TE-enabled GF plies
19 were employed for the manufacturing of both 10-ply unidirectional (UD), and cross-ply
20 composite laminates. The UD laminate generated a TE voltage (V_{TEG}) of 8.4 mV and a TE
21 current (I_{sc}) of 597.4 μA for 100 K through-thickness temperature difference (ΔT) *i.e.*, a
22 maximum power of 1.3 μW . The temperature sensing capability of the TEG-laminate was also
23 demonstrated. Three-point bending tests indicated a ca. 10% decrease in flexural properties
24 with the integration of the TEG functionality for the UD configuration.

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27 **Keywords:** Seebeck effect; Large-scale thermal energy harvesting; Carbon fiber reinforced
28 polymer composites; Functional coatings; Multifunctional composite laminates; Through-
29 thickness; Thermoelectric generator; Temperature sensor

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31 **Highlights:**

- 32 • TE-enabled GF functional ply with $57.2 \mu\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}^2$ power factor
- 33 • through-thickness TEG-CFRP laminate device with $1.3 \mu\text{W}$ power output
- 34 • through-thickness TEG-CFRP laminate device with $0.1 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ power density
- 35 • multifunctional CFRP laminate with self-powered temperature sensing capabilities

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37 **Graphical Abstract**

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48 1. Introduction

49 Sustainable energy sources are a viable response to the enormous energy demands caused by
50 human activity. Moreover, supplementary green solutions for energy generation could further
51 reduce greenhouse gases and contribute towards the climate neutrality policy milestone by 2050
52 [1]. Energy harvesting concepts can utilize diverse renewable energy sources offered amply by
53 the natural environment, and convert them to exploitable electrical power [2]. Self-powered
54 energy harvesting technologies based on, *e.g.* solar radiation, vibrations, thermal energy, *etc.*
55 are indicative routes of the above approach [3].

56 Waste heat recovery from the transportation sector and industrial processes is a promising way
57 regarding the transformation from a fossil fuel-based era to a low-carbon society [4].
58 Thermoelectric (TE) energy conversion is based on the Seebeck effect. This relates temperature
59 differences (ΔT) to induced electrical voltage (ΔV). TE power generation is feasible without
60 combustion and greenhouse gas emissions [5]. The magnitude of the induced voltage is related
61 to the material's internal density of states resulting in positive (p-type) or negative (n-type)
62 values, depending on the electronic behavior of the semi-conductor material and is given by
63 $\Delta V = S \cdot \Delta T$, where S is the Seebeck coefficient. S is employed to estimate the power factor-
64 $PF = \sigma S^2$ (PF), which is equal to the product of the electrical conductivity (σ) and the Seebeck
65 coefficient squared. This quantity is characteristic of TE efficiency of each TE material. The
66 overall TE performance is classified by the dimensionless figure of merit- $ZT = (\sigma S^2) \cdot T / \kappa$ (ZT),
67 where T is the absolute temperature and κ the thermal conductivity. Consequently, the proper
68 matching of high electrical conductivity and Seebeck coefficient, coupled with low thermal
69 conductivity is a prerequisite for adequate TE efficiency [6].

70 Low bandgap semiconductors, *e.g.* Te, Bi₂Te₃, Sb₂Te₃, Bi₂S₃, *etc.*, and their alloys, are well-
71 established as efficient TE inorganic materials [7]. Nanocomposite organic-inorganic hybrids
72 are also highly recommended by the research community. In this approach, the organic part
73 offers the necessary electrical conductivity enhancement and flexibility [8]. In this way, the
74 efficiency, the range and the potential applications of TE coatings are substantially extended
75 [9]. On the other hand, the combination of the organic part with the nanostructured inorganic
76 part results in a crystalline structure with grain boundaries. Thus, the scattering centers of
77 phonons increase owing to the shortening of the phononic mean free path [10,11]. This
78 simultaneously allows for high Seebeck coefficient and the decrease of thermal conductivity.
79 On account of this synergy, the thermal conductivity of low-dimensional materials can become

80 significantly lower than that of their bulk counterparts without the reduction of electrical
81 conductivity and the overall TE figure of merit [12,13].

82 Thermoelectric generators (TEGs) can harvest the ambient low-grade thermal energy losses to
83 provide practical, fully energy-autonomous solutions for a wide application range, which
84 require a power supply from micro Watts up to several hundreds of Watts scale [2,14]. Typical
85 TEG devices consist of multiple interconnected thermoelements, either single-type or p-/n-type.
86 These thermoelements are interconnected electrically in series and thermally in parallel.
87 Various TEG designs have been reported operating upon a wide range of ΔT . Common to all
88 designs, is the temperature difference between a heat source and a heat sink which creates an
89 electric current due to the diffusion of electrons and holes with a direction from the hot side to
90 the cold one [15–18]. However, the conversion efficiency of the present TEG devices is 3-5%
91 requiring large applied ΔT [19]. Therefore, significant research effort is devoted to improving
92 the TE performance at the material level.

93 More complex flexible [20], elastic [21] and wearable [22] architectures based on highly
94 efficient TE nanocomposite films have been proposed according to the literature. A variety of
95 scientific publications refer to improvements in TE efficiency of bulk nanocomposites *e.g.* [23],
96 as well as structural fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites [24,25].

97 FRP composites are advanced structural materials widely used in aerospace, automotive,
98 renewable energy, *etc.*. For more than a decade, nanotechnology concepts, including the
99 incorporation of nanomaterials are being employed to further enhance advanced structural
100 composites. FRPs offer the potential for flexible design via the application of novel
101 manufacturing approaches, which enables reinforcement at the nanoscale. Thus, significant
102 improvements in targeted properties may be achieved, *i.e.* enhanced fracture toughness,
103 interfacial adhesion, electrical and thermal properties [26–29]. Furthermore, a diversity of
104 added functionalities may be included in FRPs endowing thus a multifunctional character to the
105 structure. Representative studies include advanced composites with added functionalities such
106 as smart structural self-monitoring assessment and damage self-sensing [30,31], self-healing
107 potential including concurrent electrical and mechanical property recovery [32],
108 electrochemical energy storage [33], thermal energy management [34,35], piezoelectric and TE
109 energy harvesting [36,37].

110 Improving the TE efficiency of bulk structural composites has been the aim of various research
111 groups. Chung and colleagues [38] presented the design of a TE-enabled laminate with a

112 Seebeck coefficient of +82 $\mu\text{V/K}$, consisting of p- and n-type carbon fiber laminae with
113 purposely positioned junctions at the interlaminar interface. Han *et al.* reported a Seebeck
114 coefficient of +110 $\mu\text{V/K}$ achieved via ball-milled TE microparticles and carbon black as
115 interlaminar fillers within a carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) laminate [39]. Another
116 study reported the modification of polymer matrix-carbon fiber interfaces with micro-scale
117 inorganic fillers, which resulted in a Seebeck coefficient of +163 $\mu\text{V/K}$ [40].

118 Apart from their exceptional specific properties, such as high specific strength and stiffness,
119 carbon fiber (CF) reinforcements are also attractive due to their excellent conductive properties.
120 This has also encouraged their utilization as current collectors or counter electrodes upon
121 electrochemical devices fabrication, as is reported in various studies [41,42].

122 In this study, we demonstrate for the first time purposely designed structural UD and cross-ply
123 10-ply CFRP composite laminates which operate as through-thickness TEGs, *i.e.*, the
124 temperature difference- ΔT is applied along the thickness of the laminate, typically resulting in
125 high temperature gradients. As should be noted, the through-thickness configuration is of
126 particular interest as it may be readily applied in applications such as cooling circuits,
127 superheated steam ducts, thermal insulation elements *etc.*. However, it is not easy to achieve at
128 system level using planar elements such as laminae. Herein, we employ an architected
129 lamination from nano-enabled lamina to manufacture a functional TE-enabled structural
130 laminate. The manufactured durable TE coatings exhibited an in-plane Seebeck coefficient of
131 +189 $\mu\text{V/K}$, which corresponded to a power factor of 57.2 $\mu\text{W/mK}^2$. Scanning Electron
132 Microscopy (SEM) was employed to inspect the microstructural characteristics of the tellurium
133 coated GFs (GF-TE paste). Electrical and spectroscopic measurements (XRD and Raman) were
134 performed to evaluate the functional GF fabrics. Eventually, the TE-enabled GF laminae were
135 used for the manufacturing of TEG-CFRP composite laminates at different configurations. The
136 UD and the cross-ply laminates could generate 1.3 μW and 0.5 μW , respectively. The employed
137 through-thickness architecture comprised of a single thermoelement operating at a ΔT of 100
138 K. The highly conductive CF tows were exploited as electrodes of the structural TEG device.
139 The temperature self-monitoring ability of the TE-enabled UD laminate was also assessed as
140 an additional function. Finally, the mechanical properties of the proposed through-thickness
141 TEG-CFRP UD laminate were evaluated and compared to the corresponding conventional
142 CFRP UD laminate through standard three-point bending tests. An average reduction of ca.
143 10% in bending strength and bending modulus values was determined for the TE-enabled
144 laminate.

145 2. Experimental section

146 2.1 Materials

147 Telluric acid ($\text{Te}(\text{OH})_6$, 98% purity), L-Ascorbic acid (reagent grade with 99% purity),
148 cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB, $\geq 98\%$ purity) and Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, \geq
149 99%, 78.13 g/mol) organic solvent were provided by Sigma Aldrich (Missouri, USA). Poly(3,4-
150 ethylenedioxythiophene)-poly(styrenesulfonate) – PEDOT:PSS conductive polymer screen-
151 printing ink (Orgacon™ EL-P5015 with 2.5-5.5% wt. solid content) was provided by Agfa
152 (Mortsel, Belgium). RS pro silver (Ag) conductive adhesive epoxy-based paste was supplied
153 from RS Components (Corby, UK). All chemicals were analytical grade and utilized as received
154 without any further purification. Distilled H_2O , hereafter denoted as DI water, was used
155 throughout all synthetic, dilution and cleaning procedures.

156 Unidirectional stitched carbon fiber (CF) fabric (UD, 300 g/m^2) with 0.33 mm ply thickness
157 and unidirectional stitched glass fiber (GF) fabric (UD, 320 g/m^2) with 0.26 mm ply thickness
158 were procured from Braca (Kaunas, Lithuania) and Fibermax (Volos, Greece), respectively.
159 The commercial Araldite LY 5052/Aradur 5052 epoxy resin and amine-based hardener system
160 by Huntsman (Texas, USA) was employed as the composite matrix with resin to hardener
161 weight ratio 100:38% w/w. Curing was conducted under 3 MPa pressure at room temperature
162 (RT) for 24 h and post-curing at 100°C for 4 h. The T_g of the matrix is reported to be 131°C
163 according to the technical datasheet provided by the manufacturer. A Copper (Cu) foil of ca.
164 500 μm thickness was employed to create the external metallic electrodes of the TEG.

165 2.2 Development of the nanoparticle-based TE paste

166 **Figure 1** illustrates the development steps for producing the TE pastes with the different Te
167 NWs to PEDOT:PSS mass ratios. The nanostructured TE powder was synthesized following a
168 surfactant-assisted chemical reduction reaction, as was previously reported [43]. In more detail,
169 in a three-necked round reaction flask, 4.93 g of L-Ascorbic acid was dissolved in 200 ml of DI
170 water as reducing agent, and 0.1 g CTAB was added as the stabilization and nucleation agent.
171 After the homogenization of the solution, 0.277 g $\text{Te}(\text{OH})_6$ Te precursor was added while the
172 mixture was vigorously stirred. Then, the mixture was heated to 90°C for 20 h and left to cool
173 down at room temperature. The cleaning process consisted of centrifugation at 9000 rpm for 1
174 h followed by pouring off the CTAB rich supernatant so as to remove any unreacted
175 constituents. The final product was collected with vacuum-assisted filtration through a PVDF

176 membrane filter (pore size 45 μm). A thick, concentrated TE paste (200 mg/ml) was formed by
 177 fully dispersing in DI water the synthesized Te NWs powder via vigorous stirring for 30 min
 178 followed by mild bath sonication for 1 h at room temperature. In order to further improve the
 179 electrical conductivity by swelling the PSS molecules [44], 5% DMSO was added into the
 180 commercial PEDOT:PSS paste. The mechanical overhead stirrer IKA EUROSTAR 20 high-
 181 speed digital (Freiburg, Germany) with R 1389 (PTFE-coated) 3-bladed propeller was further
 182 employed for shear mixing for 15 min so as to thoroughly homogenize the TE-PEDOT:PSS
 183 paste. Three TE pastes with different Te NWs to PEDOT:PSS mass ratios were produced, *i.e.*
 184 1 to 1.25 (TE paste 1:1.25), 1 to 1 (TE paste 1:1) and 1.25 to 1 (TE paste 1.25:1).

185
 186 **Figure 1.** Process diagram for the development of the TE paste.

187 **2.3 Manufacturing of the through-thickness TEG-CFRP laminate**

188 To this end, the p-type TE paste with a specific mass ratio of 1:1 Tellurium nanowires (Te
 189 NWs) to PEDOT:PSS was employed. Subsequently, a glass fiber (GF) fabric was coated with
 190 the TE paste via a simple blade-coating and drying process. In **Figure 2a**, the double-sided
 191 blade coating of the GF fibrous substrate with the TE paste (1:1) is schematically presented.
 192 The fibers were coated while resting on a hot plate at 120°C and were left for 30 min after the
 193 coating process to allow for the complete evaporation of the solvent. The distance between the
 194 heated GF substrate and the blade was fixed at 500 μm . A continuous uniformly thick, and

195 homogeneous TE film was deposited on each side. The resulting $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ TE-enabled GF
 196 fabric is depicted in **Figure 2b**.

197 The final 10-ply TEG laminate architecture was designed to operate as a single-thermoelement
 198 through-thickness TEG device. Integral part of this architected laminate was the TE-enabled
 199 functional GF lamina. The final laminate dimension was $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$. As should be mentioned,
 200 this was delimited by the TE-enabled lamina which was purposely manufactured so as to fully
 201 exploit the laminate active surface and is inserted in-between the top CF lamina and the bottom
 202 eight CF laminae. Vitrally important to the aforementioned design was not to allow any short-
 203 cut between the bottom 8-ply CFRP which performed as an electrode for the hot side and the
 204 top single CF lamina which performed as an electrode for the cold side. More analytically, UD
 205 laminates consisting of 8 UD CF laminae (bottom electrode), 1 GF functional UD lamina and
 206 1 top UD CF lamina (top electrode) were manufactured using hand lay-up (**Figure 2c**), followed
 207 by epoxy resin impregnation and thermopressing. The symmetric cross-ply lamination
 208 consisted of 8-ply $[0/90]_{2s}$ (bottom electrode), 1 GF functional UD lamina and 1 top UD CF
 209 lamina (top electrode) at 0° orientation. Both sides of the produced laminates were slightly
 210 sanded so as to expose the conductive CF fibers. Conductive epoxy was employed to attach
 211 copper foil contacts, as shown in **Figure 2d**, which provided both electrical and thermal
 212 conductivity from both laminate sides.

213
 214 **Figure 2.** (a) Blade coating process for the TE paste (1:1) double-sided deposition onto the GF fabric, (b) TE-
 215 enabled GF functional ply, (c) lamination of the UD TEG-laminate and (d) final 10-ply through-thickness TEG-
 216 laminate.

217 *2.4 Characterization techniques*

218 The FEI NanoSem 200 (Eindhoven, Netherlands) at an operational voltage of 5 kV was
219 employed to study the morphology of the coated GF fabrics with the different TE pastes.

220 Four-probe sheet resistance measurements were conducted to determine the electrical resistivity
221 values of the double-side blade-coated GF fabrics with the various TE pastes. The Ossila Ltd
222 (Sheffield, UK) conductivity measuring setup was employed to measure the four-probe sheet
223 resistance and the electrical conductivity was subsequently calculated as $\sigma=1/R \cdot L/A \cdot (\ln 2/\pi)$,
224 where R is the e, L is the length, and A is the cross-section of each specimen. The fabricated
225 coated films onto the fibrous substrates were typically 30-40 μm in thickness. This mean value
226 was extracted from 10 measurements per specimen using a digital caliper with 0.01 mm
227 resolution.

228 An in-house manufactured setup was used to measure the Seebeck voltage. One side of the TE-
229 enabled GF fabrics was placed on an aluminum block with controlled heating, and the other
230 side on a heat sink which was kept at room temperature with water circulation to achieve a
231 stable temperature difference. The temperature of each block was measured independently
232 using K-type thermocouples. While the temperature difference between the hot and the cold
233 side was varied, the corresponding Seebeck voltage was monitored using the Agilent
234 34401A6½ (California, USA) digital multimeter. The Seebeck coefficient was calculated as the
235 slope of the temperature difference versus output voltage via linear regression.

236 X-ray diffractometry for the synthesized Te NWs buckypaper film was performed with the
237 Bruker D8 ADVANCE (Massachusetts, USA) in symmetric step-scan with a step $2\theta=5^\circ$ in
238 transmission mode. The diffractometer operated at 40 kV and 30 mA with $K\alpha$ radiation
239 ($\lambda=1.5406 \text{ \AA}$), diffraction angle (θ , $10^\circ < 2\theta < 80^\circ$), and a step size of 5° .

240 The Labram HR-Horiba (Horiba, France) micro-Raman system was used to identify the existing
241 phases present in both the TE materials and the coated GF fabric. The 514.5 nm line of an Ar^+
242 ion laser operating at a laser power of 1.0 mW at the focal plane and an optical microscope
243 equipped with a 100 \times objective served to deliver the excitation light and collect the back-
244 scattering Raman activity. All spectra were collected in the 90-2000 cm^{-1} range and were
245 normalized to the highest intensity peak for each spectrum.

246 The TE output characteristics of the through-thickness TEG-CFRP laminates were measured
247 with the aforementioned in-house setup which was purposely modified to measure the through-
248 thickness TE efficiency. More specifically, the laminate was sandwiched between the hot and

249 the cold metal block, which enabled the generation of the desired ΔT values. For all
250 measurements, the cold block was kept at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ\text{C}$) via mild water circulation,
251 while the hot block was heated at 75°C , 100°C and 125°C via calibrated temperature-controlled
252 resistors. Power output measurements were performed utilizing a specially designed custom-
253 built electronic system based on a LabVIEW-PC interface with a range of applied external load
254 resistances from 1 Ohm to 10000 Ohm with 1 Ohm resolution. All tests were performed at
255 ambient conditions (1 atm and $40 \pm 5\%$ RH).

256 In order to assess the effect of the integration of the TE capabilities in the composite, three-
257 point bending quasi-static tests according to ASTM D 790-03 standard were conducted as a
258 screening test to compare the mechanical performance of functional and non-functional
259 laminates. To this end, UD reference laminates were manufactured following the
260 aforementioned lamination *i.e.*, 8 UD CF laminae plus 1 GF UD lamina and 1 top UD CF
261 lamina, the difference being that the GF lamina was not functionally coated. Three-point
262 bending was chosen as a mechanical test due to the symmetry provided, as the expected effect
263 of the inclusion of the GF lamina is limited to a shift in the neutral axis to the opposite side of
264 the GF, which can be assumed not to affect the bending stress field. This would not be the case
265 if *e.g.*, tension was chosen as screening method, as the inclusion of the GF lamina would
266 inevitably induce out of plane stresses. For the tests, the 100 kN Universal Testing Machine by
267 Jinan Testing Equipment IE Corporation (Jinan, China) was employed. All specimens were
268 conditioned overnight by drying in an oven at 40°C before testing to eliminate humidity effects.
269 A loading speed of 1 mm/min was selected for testing the $50 \times 13 \times 3.3 \text{ mm}^3$ specimens. Six
270 specimens were tested for each UD laminate configuration (functional and reference).

271 **3. Results and Discussion**

272 *3.1 SEM investigations for the nanoparticle-based TE pastes coated onto GF fabric*

273 Blade coating is a suitable printing technique to form relatively thick TE films onto fibrous
274 substrates due to the capillary phenomena. At the same time, GFs are efficient as supporting
275 scaffolds, so as to pertain structural stability to the functional TE films [25].

276 In **Figure 3**, SEM images of the coated GF fabrics with the three produced TE pastes are
277 depicted. **Figure 3a** corresponds to GF fabric with TE paste (1:1.25), **Figure 3b** to GF fabric
278 with TE paste (1:1) and **Figure 3c** to GF fabric with TE paste (1.25:1). As can be seen,
279 homogenous nanostructured features are formed on the microscale GF reinforcing phase. The

280 efficient wetting of the fibrous substrate by the TE pastes for all cases is clearly manifested by
 281 the continuously distributed nanostructures onto the GFs. **Figure 3c** depicts a denser network
 282 of high aspect ratio typical 1D nanostructures (**Figure S1**) compared to **Figure 3a-b** [43]. As
 283 expected, this denser network resulted in superior bulk TE properties in the case of the 1.25:1
 284 TE paste. The created continuous through-thickness films cover the areas between the stitched
 285 GF tows, creating multiple bridging of interconnected TE paths. As should also be noted, due
 286 to their low thermal conductivity, the GFs in between the TE films also act as a thermal barrier,
 287 resulting in an overall reduced thermal conductivity of the structure.

288
 289 **Figure 3.** FESEM micrographs of the coated GF fabrics (a) TE paste (1:1.25), (b) TE paste (1:1) and (c) TE paste
 290 (1.25:1).

291 3.2 TE performance of the nanoparticle-based pastes coated onto GF fabric

292 Four probe sheet resistance measurements (**Figure 4a**) and the respective in-plane Seebeck
 293 voltage (**Figure 4b**) measurements were conducted to determine the electrical conductivity and
 294 the Seebeck coefficient values of the double-side blade-coated GF fabrics (25 mm×20 mm²
 295 specimens – **Table S1**) with the three different mass ratio TE pastes. The mean output values
 296 were derived from TE measurements of five specimens for each TE paste.

297 **Figure 4c** summarizes the measured TE properties. The coated GF-TE paste (1:1) exhibited an
 298 electrical conductivity of 1600 ± 2.42 S/m at RT and a $+189 \pm 4.2$ μ V/K Seebeck coefficient

299 (Figure S2), which corresponded to the maximum power factor of $57.2 \mu\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}^2$. The
 300 respective Seebeck coefficients for (1:1.25) and the (1.25:1) were $50.5 \mu\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}^2$ for and 14.4
 301 $\mu\text{W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}^2$. The positive values of the Seebeck coefficient are indicative of the p-type
 302 semiconducting character of the TE pastes-films measured at ΔT of 100 K.

303 As should be highlighted, the increase of nanoparticle content in the paste corresponds to a
 304 decrease in the electrical conductivity, while the Seebeck coefficient increases. This tradeoff is
 305 common in semiconductor TE materials, in relation to the concentration of the dopant as a
 306 decrease in carrier concentration results in a decrease in the electrical conductivity and an
 307 increase of the Seebeck coefficient [43,45].

308
 309 **Figure 4.** Schematic depiction of the in-plane (a) electrical conductivity, (b) TE measurements and (c) the
 310 respective values of the GF fabrics coated with TE pastes for different mass ratios.

311 In order to calculate the figure of merit ZT , a thermal conductivity value of ca. $0.2 \text{ W}/\text{m}\cdot\text{K}$ was
 312 utilized, as reported in the literature for similar materials [13]. A ZT of 0.11, 0.1 and 0.02 was
 313 calculated for the coated GFs with the TE paste (1:1), (1:1.25) and (1.25:1), respectively.

314 The thermal to electrical energy conversion efficiency (η) limited by the Carnot heat engine
 315 cycle efficiency was determined as $\eta = (T_H - T_C) / T_H \cdot \sqrt{(1 + ZT) - 1} / \sqrt{1 + ZT + (T_C / T_H)}$, where T_H
 316 represents the temperature of the hot side and T_C is a steady temperature of a cold side [14].
 317 The calculated energy conversion efficiencies of the coated GF-TE paste (1:1), the GF-TE paste
 318 (1:1.25) and the GF-TE paste (1.25:1) at a ΔT of 100 K were 0.77%, 0.68% and 0.2%,
 319 respectively. Consequently, the coated GF-TE paste (1:1) was selected for further experiments,
 320 as it exhibited the highest TE efficiency.

321 3.3 Spectroscopic analysis of the TE paste (1:1) onto GF fabric

322 In general, an ordered molecular structure is able to positively contribute on carrier
323 transportation phenomena [46]. The synthesized Te NWs were characterized by XRD, as shown
324 in **Figure 5a**. All peaks observed in the XRD spectra could be indexed to the reference spectrum
325 (No. 36-1452). Therefore, the Te NWs have a crystalline hexagonal structure with three atoms
326 per unit cell and cell constants a and c equal to 4.46 Å and 5.92 Å, respectively. The recorded
327 XRD patterns are well in agreement with the reported literature for Te NWs [47].

328 The selected TE paste (1:1), its constituent materials *i.e.* Te NWs and PEDOT:PSS and the
329 paste after its application onto the GF fabric were evaluated by Raman spectroscopy (**Figure**
330 **5b**). The main vibrational modes of the TE paste (1:1) were identified as a double peak centered
331 at 117 and 137 cm^{-1} that can be attributed to the A_1 and the E_2 vibrational modes of Te NWs
332 [48]. These peaks were also present at the Te NWs spectrum at 118, and 139 cm^{-1} , as well as in
333 the TE coated glass fabric at 119 and 139 cm^{-1} . A vibrational mode of minor intensity was
334 observed at 261 cm^{-1} for both the TE paste (1:1) and the TE coated GF and at 271 cm^{-1} for the
335 Te NWs. This is attributed to a second-order vibration of Te NWs [47].

336 A medium-intensity double peak was present between 1220 and 1680 cm^{-1} for the TE paste
337 (1:1) spectrum and between 1050 and 1690 cm^{-1} for the TE coated GF. This was not present at
338 the spectrum of the as-synthesized Te NWs. This complex double shoulder is very broad and
339 can be assigned to the asymmetric C=C stretching vibrations, the C-C stretching and the
340 symmetric (C=C)-O stretching of PEDOT. Although, this weak contribution could not be
341 observed in the spectra of the TE paste and the TE coated GF fabric [49].

342 The spectrum of PEDOT:PSS presented several vibrational modes of very low intensity. The
343 peak centered at 437 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the SO_2 bending, the bands at 578, 853, and 988
344 cm^{-1} to oxyethylene ring deformation, the band at 704 cm^{-1} to the symmetric C-S-C
345 deformation, the band at 1128 cm^{-1} to the C-O-C deformation, the peaks at 1259 and 1370 cm^{-1}
346 to C-C stretching, the band at 1431 cm^{-1} to C=C(-O) stretching, and finally the vibrational
347 modes centered at 1496, 1541 and 1569 cm^{-1} to asymmetric C=C stretching [49]. However,
348 these bands did not substantially contribute to the spectra of TE paste (1:1) and the TE coated
349 GF fabric as their relative intensity is significantly lower.

350

351 **Figure 5.** (a) XRD pattern of the synthesized Te NWs backpaper film and (b) normalized Raman spectra of the
 352 constituent TE materials, as well as the coated GF with TE paste (1:1).

353 3.4 Power output characteristics of the through-thickness TEG-CFRP laminate

354 **Figure 6a** depicts the equivalent circuit of the through-thickness measurements configuration
 355 for the presented structural TEG device. In contrast to conventional structural composites, a
 356 through-thickness TEG-CFRP multifunctional composite can effectively exploit the
 357 graphitized continuous CFs and contribute to the electrical and thermal properties of the
 358 laminate. CFs possess high electrical and thermal conductivity in the in-plane direction, but
 359 generally present relatively poor Seebeck coefficient values [38].

360 In **Figure 6b**, the through-thickness electrical and TE response for the reference 10-ply UD and
 361 cross-ply CFRP laminates at a ΔT of 100 K are compared. Both reference CFRP composites
 362 exhibited a through-thickness electrical resistance in the range of 5–30 Ohm, while the through-
 363 thickness Seebeck TE voltage was as low as 0.3 to 0.4 mV at a through-thickness temperature
 364 difference of 100 K. Chung *et al.* [39] reported similar values of ca. 0.3 mV for a cross-ply
 365 CFRP laminate at various curing pressures.

366 On the other hand, the 10-ply UD and cross-ply TEG-laminates exhibited TE voltages (V_{TEG})
 367 of 8.4 ± 0.35 mV and 7.9 ± 0.48 mV with generated short-circuit current (I_{sc}) of 597.4 ± 22.4
 368 μA and 220.2 ± 25.1 μA at a ΔT of 100 K, respectively. The TE output was reported from
 369 independent measurements of five manufactured laminates for each category. The TE power
 370 output was also calculated as [50]: $P_{max} = \Delta V^2 / 4 R_{TEG}$ at a ΔT of 100 K. The UD TEG-laminate
 371 produced ca. 1.3 μW and the cross-ply TEG-laminate ca. 0.5 μW . The respective power density
 372 (normalized by the functional active area of the laminate) was 0.1 W/m^2 and 0.05 W/m^2 for UD
 373 and the cross-ply TEG-laminates, respectively.

374 At this point, it is worth mentioning that the through-thickness internal electrical resistance at
 375 RT (R_{TEG}) prior to the epoxy resin encapsulation was 6.7 ± 0.4 Ohm for the UD lamination and
 376 27.2 ± 0.7 Ohm for the cross-ply lamination. After resin impregnation and curing, the R_{TEG}
 377 values at RT were almost identical for both composite laminates, proving that the TE-enabled
 378 GF functional ply was chemically stable (**Figure S3**) and not reactive to the matrix
 379 environment. As expected, as the R_{TEG} values determine the TE power output and the efficiency
 380 of the structural TEG laminate depends strongly on the lamination sequence.

381
 382 **Figure 6.** (a) Through-thickness measurement configuration and TEG equivalent circuit, (b) Electrical and TE
 383 response for the UD, and the cross-ply TEG laminates at 100 K ΔT .

384 **Figure 7a** shows the through-thickness thermal energy harvesting capabilities of the
 385 manufactured TEG-CFRP laminates. Otherwise, the resulted power output appears to be
 386 inadequate. However, due to the TE response of the coated GF-TE paste (1:1), when the
 387 manufactured TEG-laminate is exposed to a temperature difference between the bottom and the
 388 top side in the through-thickness direction, a significant TE power is generated on account of
 389 the Seebeck effect.

390 **Figure 7b-c** depict the specific power output characteristics for the 10-ply UD TEG-laminate,
 391 and **Figure 7d-e** present graphs for the respective 10-ply cross-ply TEG-laminate at various
 392 ΔT . Specifically, the plots show the output voltage-current (V-I), the output power-current (P-
 393 I), the output V- R_{LOAD} and the output P- R_{LOAD} curves with the application of different external
 394 load resistances (R_{LOAD}). The dots represent the experimentally measured values, while the
 395 continuous lines have been calculated by the following equation [43]:
 396 $P = I^2 R_{LOAD} = (V_{TEG} / (R_{TEG} + R_{LOAD}))^2 R_{LOAD}$. For both 10-ply TEG-laminates, when the R_{LOAD} is
 397 equal to the experimental value of the R_{TEG} , the maximum TE power generation is being

398 observed. As expected, the TE voltage output for the various applied R_{LOAD} was inversely
 399 proportional to the output current, resulting in the representative parabolic behavior.

400

401

402 **Figure 7.** (a) Through-thickness UD TEG-laminate at $\Delta T=100$ K, power output of TEG-laminates at ΔT 50, 75
 403 and 100 K (b, c) UD and (d, e) cross-ply.

404 A 55.5% and a 58.2% decrease in the through-thickness TE voltage values for the UD laminate
 405 (8.4 ± 0.35 mV) and the cross-ply laminate (7.9 ± 0.48 mV), respectively, were observed
 406 compared to the in-plane TE voltage (18.9 ± 0.22 mV) of the coated TE-enabled GF fabric. The
 407 aforementioned measured values resulted from 100 K of ΔT , but the interelectrode distance was
 408 substantially reduced in the through-thickness direction (ca. 0.3 mm, corresponding to the

409 thickness of the TE-enabled GF ply) compared to the 25 mm for the in-plane TE of the coated
410 TE-enabled GF fabric, as also previously observed, *e.g.* [37].

411 Based on the above, it is evident that the manufactured multifunctional laminates possess the
412 potential for thermal energy harvesting for various practical applications. The resulted values
413 correspond to a single thermoelement structural TEG-laminate devices. As should be noted, the
414 device efficiency can further improve using multiple in-series or in-parallel interconnected
415 thermoelements in order to optimize the total TE power output in relation to the employed TE-
416 enabled active area [22].

417 Further functionalities may also be imparted to the composite via the integration of the
418 functional lamina. To this end, the temperature sensing abilities were also evaluated for the UD
419 TEG-laminate (**Figure 8**). Typical temperature sensors are based on thermocouples or resistive
420 elements [38,51]. **Figure 8a** presents the TE voltage as a function of time, which was attained
421 at ca. 252 s to an applied temperature of 125°C, upon exposure of the UD TEG-laminate to the
422 respective ΔT . Similar dependency of temperature input to voltage response has also been
423 reported in former studies *e.g.* [51] related to self-powered temperature sensors concepts based
424 on TEG devices.

425 **Figure 8b** demonstrates the TE voltage output of the TEG-laminate exposed to an applied
426 temperature of 125°C during heating-cooling cycles so as to demonstrate the function,
427 performance and response of the device as a temperature sensor. The laminate was repeatedly
428 positioned on the 100 K temperature difference stage until it reached the hot stage temperature
429 and then removed for 155 s. As can be seen, the TE voltage resulted in a 29.3% decay every
430 155 s upon cooling by removing the laminate from the 100 K temperature difference stage.
431 Reversible and almost identical TE voltage values fluctuation upon reposition and removal
432 were measured for all the recorded heating-cooling cycles.

433 **Figure 8c** presents the generated TE voltage stability *vs.* time measurements at different applied
434 temperatures of 75, 100 and 125°C for a 10-ply UD through-thickness TEG-laminate. For each
435 temperature difference, the TE power output was monitored for a total duration of 600 s.
436 Remarkably steady TE voltage values have been observed, with corresponding power
437 generation.

438 Summarizing, the integration of the TE-enabled functional lamina in the structural composite
439 can additionally pertain the self-powered temperature sensing functionality without the need
440 for embedded or externally adhered measuring sensors.

441

442 **Figure 8.** (a) TE response and (b) TE voltage variation of the CFRP-based thermocouple voltage exposed to an
 443 applied temperature of 125°C during heating-cooling cycles, (c) TE power generation during time evolution upon
 444 different applied temperatures for the 10-ply UD TEG-laminate.

445 3.5 Evaluation of the through-thickness TEG-CFRP laminate mechanical performance

446 **Figure 9** presents bar charts with the respective strength and modulus values (**Figure 9a**) and
 447 the corresponding optical microscopy images of the three-point bending failed specimens
 448 (**Figure 9b-c**). More specifically, for the UD laminates, a bending strength of 1101.9 ± 23.2
 449 MPa and a bending modulus of 46.7 ± 6.8 GPa for the TEG-laminate was measured. The values
 450 for the respective reference plain UD CFRP laminate were 1212.1 ± 21.4 MPa and 51.4 ± 6.1
 451 GPa.

452 Concluding, the multifunctional laminate exhibited a deterioration in mechanical properties of
 453 10% in bending strength and 10.1% in bending modulus compared to the reference CFRP
 454 laminate specimens. Although this property reduction is not negligible, it should be noted that
 455 the present work is focusing on demonstrating the functionalities and not in optimizing the
 456 mechanical performance.

457

458 **Figure 9.** Three-point bending tests: UD reference CFRP vs. UD through-thickness TEG-laminate (a)
 459 bending strength and bending modulus, (b, c) indicative optical microscopy images of the respective
 460 failed specimens.

461 **4. Conclusions**

462 In this work we successfully manufactured CFRP composite laminates with through-thickness
 463 thermal energy harvesting capabilities, without considerable effect on the structural integrity of
 464 the laminate. The approach used in this work involved the design, manufacturing and testing of
 465 a functional TE-enabled GF system ply which was purposely laminated within a CFRP
 466 composite to create a structural through-thickness TEG architecture. The highly conductive CF
 467 reinforcing laminae were employed as structural electrodes for the device. In relation to the TE
 468 response, the UD lamination was found to be more efficient generating a maximum electrical
 469 power output of $1.3 \mu\text{W}$ at 100 K through-thickness temperature difference. Additionally, the
 470 UD TEG-laminate exhibited also temperature self-sensing capability with short response times.

471 Self-powered architected composites allow for the realization of sustainable and self-
 472 sufficient smart structures. These are able to provide alternative energy as an electric power
 473 backup for battery-free low-power consuming electronic devices *e.g.*, wireless sensor nodes
 474 (WSNs) and Internet of Things (IoT) applications.

475 CFRPs with enhanced through-thickness thermoelectric power in the range of several μW are
 476 envisaged to harvest thermal energy at large-scale during their operational lifetime in the
 477 aerospace, automotive, aeronautics and renewable energy fields, where temperature gradients
 478 exist. Consequently, a route to self-powered recording of the exposure history of the

479 component/ structure to thermal fields could be emerged, eliminating the need for external
480 sensors as only the existing functional reinforcing phases perform also this task.

481 **Author Contributions:** GK: conceptualization, methodology, writing, visualization; LT:
482 conceptualization, visualization, review and editing; KT: XRD and Raman measurements and
483 analysis, review; CKM: validation and visualization; ML: SEM imaging and editing; ASP:
484 conceptualization, review and editing, supervision and project administration. All authors have
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